

HMC3 (CRL-3304) Protocol

Description:

- **Organism:** Homo sapiens, human
- **Cell type:** microglial cell
- **Tissue:** Brain
- **Age:** embryo
- **Morphology:** macrophage
- **Derivation:** HMC3 cell line was established through SV40-dependent immortalization of a human foetal brain-derived primary microglia culture.
- **BSL 2**
- **Growth properties:** adherent
- **Cells per vial:** approximately 2.5×10^6
- **Volume:** 1 mL
- **Comments:** resting HMC3 cells were strongly positive for the microglia/macrophage marker IBA1, positive for the endotoxin receptor CD14, but negative for the astrocyte marker GFAP. Markers of activated microglia, namely MHCII, CD68 and CD11b were negative in resting HMC3 cells, but upregulated after activation by IFN-gamma (10 ng/mL, 24h)
- **Specific applications:** neuroscience, neuroinflammation.
The transformed human microglial cells retain the properties of primary microglial cells. They represent homogeneous cell populations which can be grown indefinitely and might represent a convenient system for the biochemical analysis of the functions of microglial cells. As demonstrated by preliminary experiments, they can also support subsequent transfections which would allow study of the regulation of expression of various transfected genes in microglial cells.

Complete medium:

- EMEM
- 56 mL FBS
- 1% Penicillin/Streptomycin
- 1% L-glutamine

Reagents for cryopreservation:

Complete growth medium supplemented with 5% DMSO.

Thawing the cells:

1. Thaw the vial by gentle agitation in a 37°C water bath. To reduce the possibility of contamination, keep the O-ring and cap out of the water.
Thawing should be rapid (approximately 2')
2. Remove the vial from the water bath as soon as the contents are thawed and decontaminate by dipping in or spraying with 70% ethanol. All the operations from this point on should be carried out under strict aseptic conditions
3. Transfer the vial contents to a centrifuge tube containing 9 mL complete culture medium and spin at 125 xg for 5-7'
4. Resuspend cell pellet with the recommended complete medium. It is important to avoid excessive alkalinity of the medium during recovery of the cells. It is suggested that, prior to the addition of the

vial contents, the culture vessel containing the complete growth medium be placed into the incubator for at least 15' to allow the medium to reach its normal pH (7.0 to 7.6)

5. Incubate the culture at 37°C in a suitable incubator

Subculturing procedure:

Volumes used in this protocol are for 75 cm² flask.

1. Remove and discard culture medium
2. Wash with PBS
3. Add 2.0 to 3.0 mL of Trypsin-EDTA solution to flask and observe cells under the microscope until cell layer is dispersed (5-15'). Warning: to avoid clumping do not agitate the cells by hitting or shaking the flask while waiting for the cells to detach. Cells that are difficult to detach may be placed at 37°C to facilitate dispersal.
4. Add 6.0 to 8.0 of complete growth medium and aspirate cells by gently pipetting
5. Add appropriate aliquots of the cell suspension to new culture vessels. Cultures can be established between 1x10⁴ and 4x10⁴ viable cells/cm². Warning: do not exceed 7x10⁴ cells/cm²
6. Incubate culture at 37°C

Interval: maintain culture at a cell concentration between 1x10⁴ and 2x10⁵ cell/cm²

Sub-cultivation ratio: a sub-cultivation ratio of 1:3 to 1:8 is recommended

Medium Renewal: 2 to 3 times per week

ATCC Number: CRL-3304
Designation: HMC3 Clone 3

Low Density

High Density